

Liquidity Analysis Of Zimbabwe Stock Exchange (ZSE) Listed Retail Companies Using Traditional Ratios And Cash Flow Ratios.

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Abstract:

The objective of the paper is to analyse the significance of traditional ratios compared cash flows ratios in liquidity analysis of Zimbabwe Stock Exchange (ZSE) listed retail companies, with emphasis on these impact investor decision making. The analysis covered a period of 5 years (2010-2014) consisting of companies in the same sector, with the financial information having been obtained from the companies websites. The findings are as follows:

- *Significant statistical differences exist when the current ratios as well as the quick ratio are equated with operating cash flow ratio and critical needs ratio.*
- *There exists no significant statistical difference between the interest coverage and operating margin ratio when contrasted with cash interest coverage and operating cash margin ratios.*

Traditional ratios that incorporate current and quick ratio in liquidity analysis of companies will lead to flawed investor decision making.

Key words: *Traditional ratios, cash flow ratios, liquidity, decision making, and accrual basis*

BACKGROUND

Zimbabwe has been facing economic challenges of tight liquidity, non-performing loans, low levels of production, rising formal unemployment and company closures. The purchasing managers index (PMI) for 2014 was 43.5 per cent providing further evidence of contraction in the manufacturing sector (CZI, 2014). The average manufacturing sector capacity utilization for 2013 was 39.6 per cent compared to 36.3 per cent in 2014. There has been rise in formal sector unemployment with 55 000 employees having been retrenched over a period of four years owing to deindustrialisation (Marambanyika, 2015). The rise thereof of formal unemployment has exacerbated the informalization of the economy with the informal sector accounting for 85 per cent employment (Finscope, 2012). Most companies in the retail sector rely on credit sales as a business model hence the rise of formal unemployment has reduced credit sales thereby negatively impacting profitability. To further compound the problem, the informal sector is retailing products at uneconomic prices and hence in order to compete effectively, retailers have turned to promotional activity in an effort to boost sales. As a consequence, retailers are seeking government assistance in dealing with the influx of inferior products which are being imported by vendors without restraint, and are cheaper than the high priced good quality local products (Sibanda, 2015).

According to CZI (2014), 41 per cent of competition in the manufacturing sector is from South Africa, China 30 per cent with Zambia emerging as a threat. Liquidity of retail companies becomes of paramount importance in the light of cheap imports from South Africa, China and Zambia. In 2013, Tashas supermarkets was placed under judicial management after failing to settle USD \$3 million owed creditors (Dube, 2013). Jagers closed shop with 97 creditors being owed USD \$15 million (Musoko, 2014). Buscod chain of supermarkets was liquidated due to liquidity constraints marked by an increase in the number of retail outlets in Bulawayo (Dube, 2013).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

International Accounting Standard (IAS 1 paragraph 9) reveals the objective of financial statements as providing information about a company's financial performance, financial position and cash flows that is useful for decision making for the users of financial statements. Zimbabwe stock exchange listed retail companies incorporate traditional ratios in published financial statements to assist users in the analysis of company performance. Traditional ratios which have been widely accepted are affected by accounting policies, judgements and window dressing compared to cash flow ratios that cannot be easily manipulated and are not affected by accounting policies and judgments. Cash flow ratios, an alternative, reveal the relationship between profitability and a company's cash generating ability as cash is the lifeblood of any business.

The research seeks to analyse liquidity of ZSE listed retail entities with the objective of revealing significant statistical differences, if any, between traditional ratios and cash flow ratios. The analysis seeks to equip users of financial statements with appropriate ratio analysis for assessing liquidity in order to enhance decision making as there is limited research in this area in Zimbabwe.

HYPOTHESIS

H₀ There exists no significant statistical differences when traditional ratios are contrasted with cash flow ratios in the liquidity analysis of ZSE listed retail companies.

H₁ Significant statistical differences exist when traditional ratios are contrasted with cash flow ratios in the liquidity analysis of ZSE listed retail companies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Fabozzi & Peterson (2003) state liquidity as reflecting a company's ability to meet short term obligations by utilising assets that are readily convertible into cash. Its importance underscored when companies fail to meet obligations to their creditors and other stakeholders as they arise.

IAS 1 paragraph 27 states that entities must prepare financial statements using accrual basis accounting with the exception of the cash flow information. Therefore, in the analysis of liquidity using traditional ratios, use is made of the current ratio and quick ratio with financial data for their computation having been obtained from financial statements prepared on an accrual basis. The current ratio reveals that ability of the company to meet current obligations at a point in time by comparing the current assets to current liabilities, with retailers being able to operate with a ratio of 0.50 :1 (Elliott & Elliott, 2013). The quick ratio signifies an entity's liquid strength in settling current obligations with the exclusion of inventory from its current assets (Elliott & Elliott, 2013). In the analysis of liquidity, use is also made of interest cover ratio where the profit before interest and tax is divided by the interest payable to assess a company's ability settle its interest obligations from profit generated from operations (Fabozzi & Peterson, 2003). Operating margin underscores the ability of an entity's earning potential per dollar in sales. Other ratios utilised in the measurement liquidity are inventory turnover, accounts receivable collection days and payables payment period (Fabozzi & Peterson, 2003).

IAS 7 paragraph 4 outlines the following as benefits of cash flow information:

- Furnishes information to the user that enables evaluation of changes in net assets, financial structure incorporating liquidity and solvency;
- Assists in evaluating whether an entity can generate cash and cash equivalents;

- Enhances comparability of present values of future cash flows of different entities by users of financial statements.
- The effects of utilising different accounting treatment for transaction and events is eliminated

The statement of cash flow ratios evaluate a company's ability to generate cash over a period of time. The cash flow ratio compares the cash from operations to current liabilities with a higher ratio preferable (Mills and Yamamura, 1998). The critical needs cash coverage ratio, provides an understanding into the company's ability to meet current obligations by dividing net operating cash flow plus interest paid with total current liabilities and interest (Atieh, 2014). The benchmark for comparison is the industry average to derive operating capability. The cash interest coverage ratio can be used as a comparative to the interest cover ratio with caution, as the cash flow from operations excludes depreciation, whilst the profit before interest and tax includes this component hence the cash interest cover will tend to be slightly higher (Mills and Yamamura, 1998). The cash operating margin evaluates an entities ability to convert sales into cash by comparing the entities operating cash flow to net sales (Porwal and Jain, 2013).

Previous studies

Kirkham (2012), in a study of liquidity of 25 Australian telecommunications companies using traditional and cash flow ratios reveals that decisions based on traditional ratios would be erroneous as differences existed between the cash flow ratios and traditional ratios. Kajanathan and Velnampy (2014), in a study of liquidity, solvency and profitability of the Sri Lanka telecommunications sector using traditional and cash flow ratios, revealed that differences existed between cash flow and traditional ratios. Jooste (2007) in a study of failed and healthy companies using cash flow ratios in South Africa reveals that the higher the ratio computed from the cash flow statements, the better the chances of survival as this indicate cash flows. A study by Atieh (2014) on "Liquidity analysis using cash flow ratios as compared to traditional as ratios in the pharmaceutical sector in Jordan," reveals liquidity analysis of companies based on traditional ratios leads to incorrect decision as there are differences between traditional ratios and cash flow ratios.

METHODOLOGY

The research focused on the comparison between traditional ratios and cash flow ratios in the analysis of liquidity of ZSE retail companies. The data was obtained from the companies' websites for the period 2010 to 2014. Three companies were utilised in the study as Lifestyle holding delisted from the ZSE. The traditional ratios and cash flow ratios were juxtaposed are listed below:

Traditional ratios		Cash flow ratios	
Ratio	Formula	Ratio	Formula
Current ratio	$\frac{\text{Current assets}}{\text{Current liabilities}}$	Cash flow ratio	$\frac{\text{Net operating cash flow}}{\text{Current liabilities}}$
Quick ratio	$\frac{\text{Current assets} - \text{Inventory} - \text{prepayments}}{\text{Current liabilities}}$	Critical needs cash coverage	$\frac{\text{Net operating cash flow} + \text{interest paid}}{\text{Current liabilities} + \text{interest paid}}$
Interest coverage	$\frac{\text{Earnings before interest and tax}}{\text{Interest expense}}$	Cash interest coverage	$\frac{\text{Net operating cash flow} + \text{interest} + \text{tax}}{\text{Annual interest}}$
Operating income margin	$\frac{\text{Net operating income}}{\text{Net sales}}$	Operating cash margin	$\frac{\text{Net operating cash flows}}{\text{Net sales}}$

Source: Atieh (2014)

Non-parametric test (Mann Whitney (U) test) was used to identify the significance of statistical differences between the traditional ratios and cash flow ratios.

ANALYSIS

The following are results of ratio analysis from secondary data.

<u>OK ZIMBABWE</u>						
Traditional Ratios	Years	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Current Ratio		1.09	1.52	1.52	1.30	1.57
Quick Ratio		0.2	0.32	0.32	0.33	0.43
Interest Cover		1.92	53.39	32.82	23.06	58.93
Operating income Margin		1.40	2.10	3.70	3.70	2.80
Cash Flow Ratios	Years	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Cash Flow Ratios		-0.08	0.19	0.29	0.36	0.35
Critical needs cash ratio		-0.02	0.19	0.40	0.36	0.35
Cash interest coverage		0.36	58.77	38.87	30.34	72.64
Operating cash margin		0.30	2.30	4.40	4.49	3.50

Comment: Cashflow ratios (cash flow ratio and critical needs cash ratio) display a much weaker liquidity position than is revealed by traditional ratios(current ratio and quick ratio). Cash flow ratios (cash interest coverage and operating cash margin) are slightly higher than traditional ratios (interest cover and operating income margin). The company is able to generate enough cash to meet its obligations as they fall due.

<u>TRUWORTHS ZIMBABWE</u>						
Traditional Ratios	Years	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Current Ratio		1.21	1.35	1.30	1.69	1.37
Quick Ratio		0.62	0.74	0.71	0.88	0.67
Interest Cover		2.56	2.33	0.97	1.12	-0.01
Operating income Margin		7.30	10.30	4.90	5.90	0.00
Cash Flow Ratios	Years	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Cash Flow Ratios		-0.42	-0.28	-0.06	0.03	0.06
Critical needs cash ratio		-0.32	-0.16	0.04	0.14	0.12
Cash interest coverage		-4.98	-2.33	0.31	0.30	0.67
Operating cash margin		-15.00	-10.30	-1.60	1.60	3.80

Comment: Cashflow ratios (cash flow ratio and critical needs cash ratio) reflect a fairly weak liquidity position compared to traditional ratio (current ratio and quick ratio). Operating cash margin slightly improved from -15.00 (2010) to 3.80(2014) whilst the interest cover declined from 7.30 (2010) to 0.00 (2014). Cash interest coverage is marginally higher than interest cover. The company is not generating enough cash to meet interest payment as they fall due though the ratio improved significantly from -4.98 (2010) to 0.67 (2014).

EDGARS ZIMBABWE

Traditional Ratios	Years	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Current Ratio		1.10	1.33	2.54	2.76	2.67
Quick Ratio		0.67	0.86	1.84	1.85	1.94
Interest Cover		2.05	2.62	2.94	4.41	2.21
Operating income Margin		11.20	14.60	13.20	11.80	6
Cash Flow Ratios	Years	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Cash Flow Ratios		-0.52	0.08	0.07	0.28	-0.13
Critical needs cash ratio		-0.38	0.19	0.21	0.36	-0.02
Cash interest coverage		-4.40	1.60	1.72	3.68	-2.34
Operating cash margin		-25.50	8.90	7.70	9.90	-6.30

Comment : Cash flow ratios divulge a weaker liquidity position than traditional ratios for the company in the period under review.

Statistical tests

A test for normality of data was undertaken with the results in the table below:

Table 1 test for normality of data.

Normality						
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	Df	Sig.
current	.187	30	.009	.922	30	.031
Quick	.188	30	.008	.858	30	.001
interest	.382	30	.000	.693	30	.000
opearting	.209	30	.002	.826	30	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

The Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests reveal the data is not normally distributed as $p < 0.05$. The results mean that the differences between the traditional ratio and cash flow ratio can be analysed using non-parametric Mann-Whitney test.

Mann-Whitney test output in terms of mean rank and the sum of ranks for traditional ratios and cash flow ratios is summarised in the table below:

Table 2 traditional ratios and cash flow ratios (Ranks)

		Ranks		
	Category	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
current	Traditional	15	23.00	345.00
	Cashflow	15	8.00	120.00
	Total	30		
quick	Traditional	15	21.87	328.00
	Cashflow	15	9.13	137.00
	Total	30		
interest	Traditional	15	18.07	271.00
	Cashflow	15	12.93	194.00
	Total	30		
operating	Traditional	15	18.53	278.00
	Cashflow	15	12.47	187.00
	Total	30		

In table 2 above, traditional ratios have higher mean rankings compared to cash flow ratios. In order to determine the significance of the differences, the actual test statistics are as per the table below:

Table 3 Traditional ratios and cash flow ratios test statistics.

	Test Statistics ^b			
	current	quick	Interest	operating
Mann-Whitney U	.000	17.000	74.000	67.000
Wilcoxon W	120.000	137.000	194.000	187.000
Z	-4.667	-3.963	-1.597	-1.887
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.110	.059
Exact Sig. [2*(1-tailed Sig.)]	.000 ^a	.000 ^a	.116 ^a	.061 ^a

a. Not corrected for ties.

b. Grouping Variable: category

Table 3 indicates that there exists significant statistical differences between current ratio and quick ratio ($p < 0.001$) when contrasted with cash flow ratio equivalent. When the interest coverage ratio and the operating profit margin are contrasted with cash interest coverage together with the cash flow margin, there are no significant statistical differences.

CONCLUSION

In the assessment of Zimbabwe Stock Exchange listed retailers, Cash flow ratios are more stringent in liquidity analysis than traditional ratios, thereby enhancing the quality of investor decision making.

REFERENCES

- Atieh, S.(2014). Liquidity Analysis Using Cash Flow Ratios as Compared to Traditional Ratios in the Pharmaceutical Sector in Jordan. *International journal of Financial research*, 5(3), 146-158.
- Confederation of Zimbabwe industries.(2014) Manufacturing Sector Survey. Available from: <http://www.czi.co.zw/images/2014.pdf>
- Dube, M.(2013). Oversubscribed Byo retail sector crumbles. *The Standard*. Retrieved May 22, 2015 from <http://www.thestandard.co.zw/2013/01/13/oversubscribed-byo-retail-sector-crumbles>.
- Elliott, B., Elliott,J. (2013). *Financial Accounting and Reporting*(16th Edition).Pearson Education.
- Fabozzi F.J, & Peterson P, P. (2003). *Financial Management and Analysis*, 2nd Edition, John Wiley & Sons Inc.
- Field, A. (2009). *Discovering Statistics Using SPSS.*, 3rd Edition, SAGE Publications Ltd.
- FinMark Trust. (2012). *FinScope MSME Survey Zimbabwe 2012*. Available from http://www.finmark.org.za/wp-content/uploads/pubs/FinScope_Zimbabwe_Broch13FNL.pdf
- International Accounting Standard Board.(2013) *International Financial Reporting Standards*. London. International accounting standards committee foundation
- Jooste,L. (2007). An evaluation of the usefulness of Cash Flow Ratios to Predict Financial Distress.*Actacommerci.co.za.*, 1-12.
- Kajananthan,R., &Velnampy.T. (2014). Liquidity, Solvency and Profitability Analysis Using Cash Flow Ratios and Traditional Ratios: The Telecommunication Sector in Sri Lanka. *Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 5(23), 163-171.
- Kirkham, R. (2012). Liquidity Analysis Using Cash Flow Ratios and Traditional Ratios: The Telecommunications Sector in Australia. *Journal of New Business Ideas and trends*, 10(1), 1-13
- Marambanyika, A. (2015, January). No repiste to job losses. *The Worker*, p.1
- Mills,J., & Yamamura, J. (1998). The power of Cash Flow Ratio.*Journal of Accounting*, 186(4), 53-61
- Musoko, C.(2014). Jagggers disposes of remaining assets, creditors to receive dividend before year end. *The Source*.Retrieved Retrieved April 16, 2015, from
- Sibanda, G.(2015). Retailers cry foul over vendors. *The Herald*. Retrieved May 22, 2015, from <http://www.herald.co.zw/retailers-cry-foul-over-vendors>
- http://africanfinancials.com/company_list.aspx?countryUID=15.